

FLUID CIRCULATION IN COUPLED FREE AND POROUS DOMAINS: IMPLICATIONS OF POROUS MEDIA HETEROGENEITY

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ABSTRACT

Development of flow cells (fluid circulation) in coupled flow in free and porous domains, particularly when the porous medium is heterogeneous, is not very well characterised/understood at the moment. This is because the free/porous interfacial properties (e.g., shear-stress) that determine the coupled flow behaviour are difficult to determine experimentally under hydro-environmental conditions. On the other hand, the implications of various forms of heterogeneity in the porous media properties can be very different on the fluid flow behaviour in the porous domains and hence, the overall flow behaviour. Our previous work suggests that fluid in porous section may circulate because of variable pressure distributions in the domain. In this paper, we aim to analyse how porous media heterogeneity affects the development of flow cells/circulation in porous section of a coupled free and porous domain and subsequently the overall flow. For this purpose, we analyse coupled flow for several patterns made up of two porous layers with differing permeabilities. An in-house graphical package has been created specifically for coupled flow problems, which aid in the visualisation of otherwise complex flow patterns.

1. INTRODUCTION

Problems involving fluid flow in adjacent free and porous domains are found in many hydro-environmental conditions, e.g., underground lake-subsurface interactions, flow in vugs/fissures, conjunctive surface and subsurface flow, and others. Free-flow regimes are generally represented by the fluid dynamical characteristics (e.g. velocity field) and may come in the form of a fluid layer or pipe, etc. However, porous flow regimes require both the characterisation of the fluid dynamics and the medium (e.g. medium permeability and velocity field). Methods to characterise flow behaviour in individual flow domains are well developed. However, the most difficult problems in the study of coupled flow behaviour has been the development of a universally applicable simulation scheme for combining the flow regimes. In the previous studies on coupled free and porous flow, it has been shown that flow circulation may occur in the porous domain due to variable pressure distributions (Das and Nassehi, 2003; Das et al. 2002, 2005). Heterogeneities in the porous domain affect the structure and dynamics of these flow cells (Carr and Straughan, 2003; Das et al., 2005). However, these studies have been limited to very simple cases (see, e.g., Figure 1) where the porous medium is made up of two vertical porous layers with different permeabilities or two-dimensional domains. Therefore, it is difficult to obtain general conclusions on the effects of porous media heterogeneity on the coupled free and porous flow behaviour. This paper aims to further these

investigations by looking at different cases of layering and thereby attempting to find a general explanation (or pattern) in the fluid circulation in coupled free and porous flow behaviour. A computational model has been developed to simulate these conjunctive flow problems, which has been well documented and discussed in several previous papers (Das, 2001; Das and Nassehi, 2001; Das, 2002; Das et al. 2002; Das and Nassehi, 2003; Das et al., 2005). However, an area that is less well developed in the previous studies is the visualisation of the complex flow patterns encountered in this problem. To eliminate this gap, a graphical user interface (GUI) has been created in this work. The GUI contains many post processing options and provide a comprehensive tool for the analysis of hydrodynamics and contaminant motion (not discussed in this paper) in coupled free and porous flow domains.

2. FORMULATION OF THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The conservation of momentum in the free flowing fluid is governed by the Navier-Stokes equation:

$$\nabla P_f = -\rho \frac{D\mathbf{v}_f}{Dt} + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v}_f \quad (1)$$

The flow in the porous domain is governed by the Darcy equation:

$$\nabla P_p = -\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_p}{\partial t} - \frac{\mu}{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{v}_p \quad (2)$$

In equation (1) and (2), the subscript ‘f’ and ‘p’ refer to the free and the porous flow domains. P and \mathbf{v} are the pressure and velocity field, respectively, while ρ and μ are, respectively, the constant density and viscosity of the fluid. \mathbf{K} is the second order tensor representation of the permeability in the porous medium.

The continuity equation for conservation of mass in both free and permeable domains are represented as,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_e = 0 \quad e \equiv f, p \quad (3-4)$$

The three components of the velocity field in the longitudinal (x-), lateral (y-) and the vertical (z-) directions are designated as u, v and w.

To couple the Navier-Stokes and Darcy’s equations, the modified form of Beavers and Joseph (1967) formulation is used (Das, 2001; Das et al., 2002; Das and Nassehi, 2003; Das et. al., 2005). Beavers and Joseph (1967) had proposed an empirical slip-flow boundary condition at the free/porous interface to describe the proportionality between the shear rate at the interface and the slip velocity through a dimensionless slip coefficient. The interfacial conditions are:

$$\text{Longitudinal velocity component (u):} \quad u_f = u_p \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Lateral velocity component (v):} \quad \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_f = \frac{\gamma_{yz}}{\sqrt{K_{yy}}} (v_f - v_p) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Transverse velocity component, w:} \quad \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right)_f = \frac{\gamma_{yz}}{\sqrt{K_{zz}}} (w_f - w_p) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Pressure (P):} \quad \left(-P + 2\mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)_f = -P_p \quad (8)$$

where, γ_{yz} is a slip coefficient at the interfacial surface characterised by only its media properties. K_{yy} and K_{zz} are the components of the permeability tensor in the lateral (y-) and the transverse (z-) directions. At the porous/porous interface (see, Figure 1), continuity of all flow variables is imposed. The boundary conditions imposed for the solution of the governing equations in the present work consist of Dirichlet type inlet and initial boundary conditions for velocity and pressure. At the exit of the porous domain, stress free boundary conditions are imposed to handle the natural flow behaviour.

FIGURE 1. Representative 3D configuration of combined free and porous domain

3. DESCRIPTION OF NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

One of the main aims of this study is to investigate how heterogeneities in porous domains affect fluid flow circulation in coupled systems. Heterogeneities are represented by two porous layers with nine different orientations (Case 1-9). These can be seen in Figure 2 along with the homogeneous domain (Case 0). To ensure that any changes in fluid flow are attributed to the heterogeneities in the porous domain, each layer is defined as being isotropic with respect to permeability and homogeneous with respect to porosity. No correlation is assumed between the material properties, e.g. the porosity and permeability. The simulations are carried out for the same degree of heterogeneity ω , which is the ratio of the smaller to the larger permeability values. A homogeneous, porous model is used as a benchmark to compare heterogeneous results against. The homogeneous domain is defined to be isotropic with respect to permeability and porosity and no correlation is assumed between them.

The main features of the computational algorithm (including boundary conditions) used to solve problems in this study have been detailed elsewhere (Das and Nassehi, 2001, 2003; Das et al. 2001, 2005). They are therefore not discussed in great length in this paper. The governing partial differential equations (equations 1-8) are discretised and reduced to algebraic forms using the standard finite volume method. The FVM is selected, as it is very good at coping with complex three-dimensional problems. Flow variables are calculated on a 3-D forward-staggered grid with cell faces being ahead

of cell nodes. Cubical cells are used for storing flow variables in both the porous and fluid regions. Pressure values are calculated at the central nodes and are the driving potential for fluid flow between adjacent cells. The u , v , w velocity components for each cell are calculated at their respective faces on the cube. For the purpose of this study volume averaged seepage velocities and pressures are calculated for each of the porous layers. In homogeneous domains, average permeability values are usually used but this does not necessarily produce accurate results in heterogeneous cases. Therefore, when solving the Darcy's equation, permeability values are specified as a function of position. It is assumed that each porous layer has a constant and isotropic permeability, which only changes at porous-porous interfaces. However, the porosity of the domain is assumed to be constant throughout all layers.

Simulations are carried out for a Newtonian fluid with constant physical properties such as density and viscosity. In this paper typical groundwater values are chosen as references. One of the domain lengths is chosen as the reference length scale for both the free and porous media. This is standard practice for combined free and porous flow simulations with the transverse y direction being used in this paper. The porous medium is assumed to be saturated with the same fluid that makes up the free-flow region. This paper concentrates on water flow but flow of any Newtonian fluid can be simulated.

4. DESCRIPTION OF GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE (GUI)

We have created an in-house MATLAB based Graphical User Interface (GUI) that is both user-friendly and contains a number of subprograms to create various types of plots to post process the numerical data of fluid flow behaviour. When opened from the MATLAB command window, a screen such as the one illustrated in Figure 3 appears. This contains a drop down menu with a number of options for visualising various types of simulated results, namely, 3D velocity profiles, 3D normalised velocity

FIGURE 2. Porous domains used in simulations

profiles, 3D pressure distributions, 3D concentrations profiles, 3D velocity and pressure plot, 3D normalised velocity and pressure plots, 1D velocity plots, 1D pressure plots and, 1D concentration plots.

FIGURE 3. GUI opening screen

FIGURE 4a. 3D velocity & pressure plot at dimensionless time step 21 in a homogeneous porous domain

For example, Figure 4(a) presents a 3D normalised velocity and pressure plot in a homogeneous porous domain. As its name suggests, this shows combined data for normalised velocity and pressure values in the chosen domain. This graph can be hard to read because of its congested nature and individual plots usually offer easier analysis of data. However, it is often necessary to have a direct relationship between the corresponding velocity profiles and pressure distributions in the domain. For example, one may wish to identify the location of the highest pressure drop and, hence, the highest fluid velocity (hence, perhaps the highest localised contaminant concentration). In such cases, the 3D normalised velocity and pressure plot is extremely useful.

As mentioned above, the new visualising tool can also plot 1D plot in the coupled free and porous domain. The one-dimensional plot is a valuable tool for the analysis of results. This developed program reads the data in the same format as the three dimensional cases for velocity, pressure and contaminant concentration. The difference in this case is that it takes the results for both the free flow and porous domains and joins the two to make one larger set of data for the whole domain. The direction that is required as a variable can be selected using the menu boxes and constant values entered for the remaining two axes. One example of a 1D profile of u-velocity component in the coupled free and porous domain (along x-axis) is shown in Figure 4(b).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 The Effects of Heterogeneity on Fluid Circulation (Flow Cells) in Porous Media

As Figure 2 shows, there are nine different types of layering looked at in this study. Flow simulations have been carried out for each case and compared to relevant homogeneous examples. Permeability values have been chosen for the two different layers (K1 and K2). Then simulations have been repeated with the layers reversed. These permeability values can be seen in Table 1 where each example is denoted by a letter after the case type (i.e. Case0A or Case0B).

FIGURE 4(b). 1D velocity plot at $y=22$, $z=22$ in free-flow & homogeneous porous domain at different time steps

FIGURE 5. Normalised velocity plot of free-flow domain at dimensionless time step 61

TABLE 1. Permeability values used for different cases

Case	Permeability K (m^2)	Case	Permeability K (m^2)
Case xA	$K_1 = 5 \times 10^{-9}$ $K_2 = 15 \times 10^{-11}$	Case xB	$K_1 = 15 \times 10^{-11}$ $K_2 = 5 \times 10^{-9}$

In the previous literature (Das et al. 2001, 2005) it has been shown that for permeability values such as those used here, flow circulations are generally attributed to variable pressure gradients. This trend has been confirmed in the current work. The subject that will be mostly discussed in this paper is the occurrence/development of flow circulation and the speed at which unidirectional flow is reached. Results can be analyzed by taking frames from the movies produced by the graphical package.

5.2 Fluid Flow in Free Flow Domain

Flow patterns in the free domain are the same for each of cases looked at in this work. Figure 5 illustrates the direction of velocity field at dimensionless time step 61. It shows water entering from the left hand boundary and flowing in an almost unidirectional path towards the free-porous interface.

5.3 Fluid Circulation in Homogeneous Porous medium (Case0A)

Case0A represents a homogeneous porous medium with a permeability of $5 \times 10^{-9} m^2$. Figure 6 shows the direction of fluid flow at a smaller time step 12 in this domain. It can be seen that water enters from both right and left boundaries causing flow circulation. Figure 7 shows the corresponding pressure distribution in the porous domain at the same time step. The plot clearly shows that circulation is attributed to variable pressure gradients in that region. This can be seen more clearly in the movies generated in this work. Figure 8 shows the direction of fluid flow in the same porous medium at time step 61. The plot shows that circulation has passed through the domain, with a state of unidirectional flow almost achieved at this time step. Figure 9 shows the corresponding pressure distribution in the porous domain at time step 61. Absence of circulation in the almost unidirectional flow pattern is mirrored by the uniform pressure

distribution observed. This further validates that fluid circulation is governed by variable pressure gradients in porous medium.

Figure 6. Normalised velocity plot in homogeneous porous domain (Case0A) at time step 12

Figure 7. Normalised pressure distribution in homogeneous porous domain (Case0A) at time step 12

5.4 Fluid Circulation in Heterogeneous Porous Medium

In this section, we discuss some typical results for two representative heterogeneous domains for the brevity of this paper. Subsequently, we draw some general conclusions in section 6. In this work, Case6A represents a heterogeneous porous medium made up of two homogeneous layers. Left and right layers have permeabilities of $5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ and $15 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$, respectively, and the porous/porous interface is inclined. Figure 10 shows fluid flow in this domain at the time step 34. Unidirectional flow has prevailed in the right hand porous layer with small amounts of circulations evident in the left. Case6B also represents a heterogeneous porous medium made up of two homogeneous layers. However, left and right layers have permeabilities of $15 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and $5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$, respectively. Figure 11 shows fluid flow in this domain at time step 34. Unidirectional flow has prevailed in the left hand layer with flow circulation being set up near the porous-porous boundary in the right. In case of Case7A, the domain represents a heterogeneous porous medium made up of two homogeneous layers. Top and bottom layers have permeabilities of $15 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and $5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ respectively. The porous/porous interface is inclined, however the direction of inclination is different to that in Case 6. Figure 12 shows fluid flow in the domain at time step 20. Both top and bottom layers show flow circulation with fluid passing through the top layer faster as it crosses the porous-porous boundary. Case7B represents the reversed where the top and bottom layers have permeabilities of $5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ and $15 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ respectively. Figure 13 shows fluid flow in the domain at the same time step, i.e., 20. Unidirectional flow has occurred in the bottom, less permeable layer with circulation occurring in the top layer near the porous-porous boundary.

6. CONCLUSION

Hydrodynamic conditions in coupled free and layered porous media have been studied in this paper. The simulations have concentrated at investigating how layering in

heterogeneous porous media affects fluid flow. The study shows that in heterogeneous cases the lower is the permeability the faster unidirectional flow occurs. Complex pressure distributions in the porous domain set up a circulation pattern (flow cells), which develops through the medium over time depending on media properties. These observations carry across into the heterogeneous layered porous with preferential flow occurring in the layer of lower permeability. This phenomenon can be explained using Darcy's equation (Equation 2). It shows that decreasing the permeability produces a larger pressure gradient both between cell nodes and globally over the entire domain, provided all other parameters remain the same. Since fluid flow follows the pattern of pressure gradients, this would attribute to an increase in the speed at which unidirectional flow is reached across the domain.

The graphical package created in this project is designed to handle 3D data. This has opened up a new forms of analysis that was previously limited in scope.

Figure 8. Normalised velocity plot in homogeneous porous domain (Case0A) at time step 61

Figure 9. Normalised pressure distribution in homogeneous porous domain (Case0A) at time step 61

Figure 10. Normalised velocity plot in heterogeneous porous domain (Case6A) at time step 34

Figure 11. Normalised velocity plot in heterogeneous porous domain (Case6B) at time step 34

Figure 12. Normalised velocity plot in heterogeneous porous domain (Case7A) at time step 20

Figure 13. Normalised velocity plot in heterogeneous porous domain (Case7B) at time step 20

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